

Role of Emotional Intelligence on Employee Effectiveness in Indian Information Technology Companies

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Abstract: Emotional Intelligence (EQ) is a set of skills that enables an individual to recognize, appraise, and manage their own emotions and the emotions of others. It is "a person's ability to monitor their thoughts and feelings in light of changing contexts, identify the emotions of others, use emotional information to guide thinking and behavior, and regulate their feelings so that they can achieve mental well-being". Emotional intelligence helps employees analyze situations with greater thoroughness. In this paper, the data is has been collected from 188 employees from ten listed Indian IT companies. The collected data's analysis indicates that employees with high emotional intelligence are more productive in their jobs. Therefore, the researcher recommends promoting emotional intelligence based on the current findings of this study.

Keywords: EQ, Employee Effectiveness, Indian IT firms, Emotional Intelligence

1. Introduction

Many Information Technology (IT) companies were started with the intention of building an emotional connect between the company and its customers as well as employees (Konrad, 2008). This new generation of IT companies has to deal with the increasing demand for emotional intelligence (EQ) in their employees. People who are effective in a variety of roles, such as sales, management, and customer service need to have knowledge about how to manage their emotions as well as other people's emotions. Emotional intelligence is an important skill to possess in order to achieve success in the business world. With emerging competition and increasing demand for employees who can handle their emotions effectively, the IT sector has been giving more motivation to recruit those candidates with more emotional intelligence. However, there is a dire need to assess this relationship using the Indian IT sector as a case study, given that Indian companies are becoming global players in terms of turnover and numbers of employees. The current

study explores the relationship between employee "effectiveness" and emotional intelligence in Indian IT companies.

The research will primarily focus on the relationship between emotional intelligence and effectiveness at work in the Indian IT sector. These findings may help (1) recruit individuals who have both traits in great abundance (2) help organisations retain high performers and (3) managers identify ways for enhancing an employee's emotional intelligence. A majority of IT companies assess their employees' performance using a matrix structure, which include factors such as quality, cost and time. However, there is hardly any emphasis on measuring the effectiveness of each employee. The study findings may help to determine whether an individual's EQ impacts his or her job effectiveness (Watkins and Menelaou, 2014).

2. Review of Literature

The term "emotional intelligence" was popularized by two prominent behavioural scientists, Peter Salovey and John Mayer (1990), who defined EQ as the set of skills that enable one to perceive, control and evaluate emotions in self and others. It is also a capability that enables one to recognise the needs of other people and respond to these needs in an effective manner. According to Mayer and Salovey (1997), an individual's EQ may be viewed as a subset of general intelligence (g). Thus, IQ contributes to the development of EQ, which in turn enhances an individual's performance.

EQ is a well-established construct in psychology and social science. According to various researchers (Alderson and Englewood, 2006; Bar-On et al. 2004; Mayer and Salovey, 1997), it is a general ability that can be learned. Emotional intelligence includes four sub-components: the perception of one's own emotions, the perception of other people's emotions, the regulation of one's own emotional responses and the regulation of emotional responses when interacting with others (Watkins and Menelaou, 2014). According to Goleman (1995), self-awareness (the ability to recognise and understand one's moods and emotions) is an important aspect of emotional intelligence. Emotional self-awareness enables an individual to understand the causes of their emotions and decide how to respond. The ability to recognise one's emotions is the key skill in emotional intelligence. It is also known as self-monitoring.

According to Goleman (1995), EQ skills are cognitive abilities such as perceiving, controlling and managing one's emotions and those of others. EQ skills can be divided into two broad categories: emotional competence and social competence. Emotional competence refers to the insight and understanding of one's own emotions. Skill in this area allows one to produce their emotions such as anger, sadness or happiness when needed. Social competence refers to the ability to understand other people's emotions, as

well as their needs in a given situation (Dyck et al., 2000). According to Goleman (1997), self-awareness is essential for effective performance in any situation where emotional intelligence is important. It fosters clarity of thought, a positive attitude and the desire to engage with other people. The better an individual is at self-awareness, the better he or she is able to use their knowledge of themselves to anticipate their own emotional responses and the responses of others. Self-awareness also includes realistic self-assessment; it means being aware of one's strengths and weaknesses.

Emotional self-control (the ability to inhibit or stop an emotional response), which directly influences behaviour, is another important aspect of emotional intelligence. According to Goleman (1995), a person who lacks self-control may react angrily when provoked, but then have difficulty calming down when the anger has passed. This problem can be solved by controlling one's emotions rather than being controlled by them. Some people suffer from emotional outbursts while others are able to maintain their self-control even when they are emotional. It is important to be able to control emotions effectively so that they do not get out of hand and have a negative effect on one's life. Emotional competence is the ability to recognise and label one's own emotions. An example is the difference between feeling bad about doing a task badly, compared with being annoyed that it was assigned in the first place (Watkins and Menelaou, 2014). In this case, emotional competence can be used to help diagnose and solve problems. Social competence is the ability to understand and appropriately respond to another person's emotions in a given situation (Dyck et al., 2000).

Watkins and Menelaou (2014) aimed to investigate the association between emotional intelligence and job performance. The study extended previous research (Watkins and Menelaou, 2014). The study used a sample of 180 employees working in a multinational retail company on two continents. This is unlike most studies that use mainly university samples or individuals working within one organisation. The researchers used a self-report questionnaire to assess the participants' EQ and job performance. The study also used a method similar to the one in Watkins and Menelaou (2014). The research was conducted within the same organisation to reduce possible confounds that may arise when comparing employees within one organisation and across different organisations. The four EQ skills were measured using the IRI (the Interpersonal Reactivity Index) (Davis, 1980; Davis, 1983) and the NEO-FFI (NEO Five Factor Inventory) (Costa and McCrae, 1992). Goleman's four facets of EQ were applied to measure this construct. Co-workers, peers and supervisors assessed the participants' job performance. The participants completed the EQ questionnaire at three different times: once at the beginning of their employment in the company, then approximately two years later and again approximately a year later. The

limitation of this study is that there was no measure of employees' EQ from other personality traits or from their work history.

In a similar study (Srivivas and Watts, 2014) the researchers measured job performance using workplace performance ratings. The participants were an equal number of men and women in the same organisation, who were part of the same department. In this study, the researchers used a more direct measure of emotional competence: the EI Questionnaire. Participants' performance was assessed in three different ways: through actual work performance evaluations, peer ratings and supervisor ratings. This prevented the confound arising because individuals may rate themselves higher than others perceive them to be (Watkins and Menelaou, 2014).

The researchers followed the same procedure used in the study by Watkins and Menelaou (2014). The study was carried out within the same organisation to reduce possible confounds that may arise when comparing employees within one organisation and across different organisations. The way EQ was measured in this study was much more direct than that of Watkins and Menelaou (2014). It measured a direct level of emotional intelligence rather than an evaluation of a person's personality traits. The advantage of using this method is that it is more effective at showing an association between EQ and job performance. Using this method, participants were asked to think about situations where they felt good or bad about themselves. The major limitation of this research is that the participants were only asked about positive and negative emotions, rather than to think about more complex emotions such as anger or fear.

This study was carried out using a sample of 188 individuals who were employed in two different organisations. In this study, EQ was measured using the Bar-on scale, which uses self-report questionnaires and can be administered without any collaboration with other individuals. The researchers measured all facets of EQ instead of Goleman's four aspects of emotional intelligence (Goleman 1995). This way, the researchers made their analysis more robust because it represents a more accurate reflection of how emotional intelligence is related to job performance (Watkins and Menelaou, 2014).

The relationship between employee "effectiveness" and emotional intelligence in the Indian IT sector is an important issue to be addressed by this study as it will allow an assessment of the correlation between these two variables. Employee "effectiveness" is a group of dimensions that evaluate how well an employee performs his or her job (Huffel, White and Anderson, 1995). This can be assessed through the effectiveness of deliverables and notable contributions during a given period (each year).

3. Methodology

Following methodology was designed for the study to collect primary data.

- Identify a sample of 188 IT employees from 10 organizations using convenience sampling (organizations were having their offices within the limits of the Mumbai Metropolitan Region)
- Design and validate a (minimum 10-point) questionnaire for ascertainment of (i) Emotional Intelligence (Bar-on Scale -133 Questions based on 5-point scale, where 1 = 'not true of me' and 5 = 'true of me.');
- ii) Level of employee effectiveness (20 items) – measured by a 5 point Likert scale that ranged from 1 for Least Effective and 5 for most effective.
- Conduct the survey
- Summarize the responses
- Apply correlation analysis and check the level of significance.
- Analyze the results

The hypotheses set in this regard were as under:

Ho1: There is no correlation between Emotional Intelligence of the employees and the employee effectiveness

Ha1: The Emotional Intelligence of the employees is positively correlated with the employee effectiveness

The study was conducted across the Mumbai Metropolitan Region (MMR).

Scheme formed for testing of hypotheses

- a) Responses were collected under 3 sections:
- b) First section of the questionnaire was dedicated to the profile information of the employees
- c) Second section was dedicated to Emotional Intelligence Scale (bar-on)
- d) Third section gathered responses for measuring the level of Employee Effectiveness.
- e) For each of the sections an average was calculated.
- f) Percentages to questions under a particular section of the questionnaire were averaged to get a single score for that section,
- g) The section-wise average score was considered for the purpose of conducting a correlation analysis.
- h) P-values were calculated, and the null hypotheses were checked for rejection or non-rejection.
- i) Cronbach's alpha score for the questionnaire was calculated the results have been discussed in the next section of the paper.

4. Results and Discussion

Table 1 shows that the values of Cronbach’s alpha was above 0.7 in each of the cases. This shows the level of internal consistency and proves the validity of the measures that have been calculated.

Table 1: Results of the Cronbach’s Alpha

Sr. No.	Section of the questionnaire	Number of Items	Cronbach’s Alpha value
1	Emotional Intelligence scores	135	0.806
2	Employee Effectiveness	20	0.789
3	Complete Questionnaire	155	0.771

Table 2. Correlations

		Emotional Intelligence	Employee Effectiveness
Emotional Intelligence	Pearson Correlation	1	.708**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.000
	N	188	188
Employee Effectiveness	Pearson Correlation	.708**	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	
	N	188	188

Note: **. Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Table 2 shows that the Emotional Intelligence scores were significantly positively correlated with the Employee Effectiveness.

R Square: This is the proportion of the variance in the response variable that can be explained by the explanatory variable. In the above table, 50.1% of the variation in employee effectiveness can be explained by the level of emotional intelligence.

Table 3: Linear Regression Analysis

Model Summary

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R ²	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	.708 ^a	.502	.499	.33373

ANOVA

Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	20.853	1	20.853	187.232	.000 ^b
	Residual	20.716	186	.111		
	Total	41.569	187			

Dependent Variable: Employee Effectiveness. Predictors: (Constant), Emotional Intelligence.

Std. Error of the Estimate: The standard error is the average distance that the observed values fall from the regression line. The observed values fall an average of 0.33373 units from the regression line.

The p-value associated with the test statistic is less than 0.05, we can conclude that the predictor variable, Emotional Intelligence is statistically significant.

5. Conclusion

The results of the study indicate that the employees with higher Emotional Intelligence are more likely to be in positions of greater responsibility and impact. The results also indicate that the level of Emotional Intelligence can predict the Employee Effectiveness in a statistically significant manner. This is consistent with the findings of other studies which found that the most successful Managerial positions were occupied by those who exhibited high levels of EQ. There does seem to be a strong positive correlation between Employee Effectiveness and Emotional Intelligence. Higher EQ increases employee effectiveness possibly because a manager with a high level of Emotional Intelligence can better coordinate the people and resources in their organization. This is done because they are more sensitive to the peoples' needs, more people friendly, more positive and have an optimistic outlook. They are also able to listen and empathize which help in getting the resources needed by their team to improve work performance. It is easier for some people to reach higher levels in an organization than others. Those who reach the top positions will tend to be those who have mastered Emotional Intelligence. Management and leadership are about understanding, motivating, and leading people. Emotional intelligence is a key component of these skills.

Managers who exhibit high levels of Emotional Intelligence tend to interact with the members of their organization in a better way than ones who do not possess these skills. They are better able to identify, understand and communicate with the different personalities in their organization. This helps them interact effectively with their subordinates, which leads to improved employee satisfaction which in turn drives employee effectiveness. Managers with a high level of Emotional Intelligence can motivate others to perform well since they can manage and lead them effectively. They do this by understanding the people that report to them as well as what motivates them. This results in increased productivity as employees are able to give of their best due to effective leadership and motivation by the manager. Employees who feel cared for by their managers will tend to work harder as opposed to ones who do not. This is because people who feel cared for are more likely to work in a way that will make the manager proud of them and this makes them feel good about themselves. Employees who feel responsible for the success of their team or organization will also be more likely to try harder in order to achieve their targets. An employee with a high EQ can empathize with other employees

and understand why they react the way they do at certain situations and circumstances. This helps them be more understanding and sympathetic of other employees' needs. This makes them better inter-personal relationship managers. This is consistent with the findings of other studies which found that the most successful Managerial positions were occupied by those who exhibited high levels of EQ.

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